

Democratising HPC Training: co-creating an Industrial HPC Nano Online Course

Xenia Ziouvelou^{1*}, Stelios Karozis^{2*}, Martina Blazkova^{3*†}
and Vangelis Karkaletsis^{1†}

^{2*}Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences and Technology, Energy & Safety, National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", Patriarchou Grigoriou & Neapoleos, Agia Paraskevi, 15310, Attica, Greece.

¹Institute of Informatics & Telecommunications, National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", Patriarchou Grigoriou & Neapoleos, Agia Paraskevi, 15310, Attica, Greece.

³Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Centro Nacional de Supercomputación, Plaça Eusebi Güell, 1-3, Barcelona, 08034, Spain.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s):

xeniaziouvelou@iit.demokritos.gr; skarozis@ipta.demokritos.gr; ;

Contributing authors: vangelis@iit.demokritos.gr;

†These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Purpose: Disruptive technologies (AI, IoT, etc) unlock new frontiers of data-centric innovation. This increases the computational needs, pushing more and more companies into the HPC space. However, although HPC is a key tool for processing and analysing the constantly growing volume of data across numerous application areas many companies remain reluctant to use HPC and move their HPC workloads to the cloud, which may be attributed to the inadequate understanding about HPC and its potential benefits, cost, security and performance aspects. At the same time, existing HPC training, mainly focus on the research and academic community, thus creating a gap in the provision of industrial HPC training and addressing the supercomputing knowledge skills of enterprises. **Methods:** Towards this aim, this paper presents an example of "massively" co-created education and training HPC module, namely an

HPC NOOC (Nano Open Online Course), targeting industrial learners. This open, agile co-creation approach incorporates key components of the European HPC ecosystem and beyond, aiming to offer a paradigm for success in the democratisation of HPC knowledge, and the co-creation of educational value aiming to reach a wide impact (i.e., educational, technological, innovation, economic impact, etc).

Results: The proposed HPC NOOC has been designed in an agile format so as to enable its ongoing evolution and expansion across emerging themes and indicative success stories across Europe and the world.

Conclusion: Acknowledging the importance of HPC as a strategic investment for Europe and the world, this paper, aims to contribute to the democratisation of HPC training for industry and narrowing the gap between HPC adoption for micro, small and medium sized enterprises is important in order to reap the benefits of HPC innovations.

Keywords: HPC, HPC professional training, co-creation, HPC democratisation, educational material, NOOC

1 Introduction - HPC & HPC Training

Disruptive technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Twins, Internet of Things (IoT) and High Performance Computing (HPC or supercomputing) unlock new opportunities for data-driven innovation across all sectors of the economy. This in turn, increases the computational needs and pushes more and more companies into the HPC space. HPC is a key tool for processing and analysing the constantly growing volume of data across numerous application areas, from 64.2 zettabytes in 2020 to an expected 180 zettabytes in 2025 (1 zettabyte is equal to 1 trillion gigabytes) [34]. As such, the industrial training requirements for HPC are intensifying as the need and pace for technological innovation is accelerating. However, the existing HPC training themes and educational forms, mainly focus on the research and academic community, thus creating a gap in the provision of industrial HPC training and addressing the supercomputing knowledge skills of enterprises.

HPC adoption across industrial sectors continues to make impressive progress, especially among large enterprises, making it indispensable for both R&D advancement and economic competitiveness. However, despite the economic benefits from HPC adoption [20], micro, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), are lagging behind in the use of this game-changing technology. SMEs tend to remain reluctant to use HPC and move their HPC workloads to the cloud, which may be attributed to the inadequate understanding about HPC and its potential benefits, cost, security and performance aspects.

This makes HPC access and knowledge as another aspect of the digital divide [18]. The so-called “HPC Digital Divide” depicts non-equitable access to high performance computing resources, and knowledge about HPC, which

can create a barrier to entry for some communities, stakeholder segments and nations, which may be difficult to bridge. As such, access to HPC resources and knowledge via targeted industrial HPC training programmes for SMEs and other relevant stakeholder segments across countries, is an imperative but at the same time, it is a challenging need that will enable us to realise the full spectrum of HPC benefits for the economy and society.

Towards this aim, democratising HPC training for industry and narrowing the gap between HPC adoption by large and small and medium sized enterprises is important in order to reap the benefits of HPC innovations. These training asymmetries can be alleviated via the provision of open, agile, industrial HPC training and targeted educational resources that match the emerging needs of industrial users especially start-ups, micro, small and medium enterprises. Leading eventually to wider access to supercomputers for scientists and engineers from the industry in addition to academia, throughout Europe and beyond.

Aiming to address these training asymmetries, an open, co-created industrial HPC training course emerged in the course of the EU-funded project EuroCC. This course was designed as a NOOC (Nano Open Online Course) micro course for industrial users to create awareness and enhance their HPC understanding and adoption of advanced computing resources to solve computationally intensive problems in their business context.

HPC as one of the key digital domains for Europe. As such, it has become a strategic investment priority [1], playing a significant role in Europe's path towards recovery [13], with an EU investment expected to significantly increase in the next Multiannual Financial Framework (2021-2027) [7]. The goal is to promote HPC services outside academia and towards the creation of a new HPC ecosystem and potential experts that could transfer the benefits of HPC to industry and public sector.

This paper presents an overview of HPC education and training, focusing on the European HPC ecosystem. It then focuses on co-creation of educational value and provides an example of this innovation approach for HPC. This example includes a (massively) co-created NOOC (Nano Open Online Course) course for HPC which is online, free, modular and self-paced targeting the needs of entrepreneurs, Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) (industrial learners in general). This EU level, HPC NOOC has been designed in an agile format that is modular, enabling its ongoing evolution and expansion across emerging themes and indicative success stories across Europe and the world. Indicative success stories from the Greek NCC are presented aiming to provide an overview of the adopted approach.

2 HPC Education and Training (EU HPC Ecosystem)

Skills in the area of High-Performance Computing (HPC) are critical not only for technology focused disciplines but also as cross-cutting elements for many

disciplines such as STEM subjects (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) and social sciences; as well as for business-oriented disciplines including the development of innovative business models and advanced industrial products. Therefore, the need for training programs and the development of digital skills and knowledge in the area of HPC, addressing the needs of the academia and industry is important. The Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) [6] focuses on the development of advanced digital skills that will support the European innovation ecosystem and will help drive innovation and digital breakthroughs. HPC and Quantum skills and related education and training programs for academia and industry focusing on fostering future experts, as well as on re-skilling and up-skilling of existing workforce through short term trainings, that will reflect the latest developments in this area. Digital Crash Courses for SMEs announced in the 2020 Skills Agenda and SME strategy.

2.1 Overview of HPC Training

The diffusion of HPC benefits and services mainly address the academic community and high-skilled programmers or administrators was the focus of many actions and frameworks in the past years [3, 29, 31, 32]. The academic community, as early adopters, is considered now heavy users of HPC infrastructures. On the other hand, HPC services in business are a slow and hard process. Most recently, specialized MSc courses were created for introducing graduate students to HPC more massively and organized [35, 33, 2]. The latter alongside a series of EU funded projects, official free online material (PRACE RI [26] and DigitalEU [10]) and dissemination of industrial success stories of HPC utilization, are part of an effort to make HPC technology mainstream and part of industrial R&D and production workflow.

It is worth mentioning that the European Centres of Excellence (CoEs)[11] for High Performance Computing (HPC) applications in HPC european ecosystem there are EU funded consortiums that are promoting the use of upcoming exascale and extreme performance computing capabilities and scale up existing parallel codes towards exascale scaling performance. Furthermore, they are try to address the skills gap in computational science in the targeted domains by specialized trainings for increased adoption of advanced HPC in industry and academia.

2.1.1 HPC MOOCs

During the last few years emerging technological tools and pedagogical models where the teaching-learning process is made online within a digital ecosystem context, have changed the educational landscape. The case of massively open, online and free courses, called MOOCs, is such an example. MOOCs aim at facilitating the acquisition and/or continuous updating of knowledge on a permanent basis through open access to high-quality educational didactic resources [30]. They are recognised as “courses designed for a large number of participants that can be accessed by anyone anywhere as long as they have

an internet connection, are open to everyone without entry qualifications, and offer a full/complete course experience online, for free” [16]. MOOCs are asynchronous, and are thus considered as a sustainable method for offering courses in Europe and continue to increase since European institutions have positive experiences for the added values of MOOCs [16]. Research in the area shows that the personal interest and level of involvement has a key impact of MOOC-based learning and the lack of motivational parameters is in some cases associated with dropping out of a MOOC [28].

The applicability of Massively Open Online Courses for scaling High Performance Computing (HPC) training and education, is starting to gain research attention [22, 17]. MOOCs provide a means for scaling and expanding the accessibility of HPC education and training, due to their open, asynchronous, learner-focused approach, however there are significant challenges that emerge from HPC’s specific training needs that should be accounted for [22].

In the context of HPC, a number of MOOC programs exist in Europe. In particular, a course focusing on “Supercomputing” [25], was developed on behalf of the Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE) by EPCC at The University of Edinburgh in collaboration with SURFSara from the Netherlands. This Supercomputing MOOC course provides an introduction to supercomputers, high performance computing (HPC) and to the technological breakthroughs in the field. It aims to enhance learners’ (with basic digital skills) understanding regarding how supercomputers function and how the development of computer simulations contributes to scientific, industrial and academic solutions and breakthroughs. This is a free, instructor-led MOOC that is offered online, via the Futurelearn platform [14]. Its duration is 5 weeks with an average commitment of 3 hours per week. Learners, are able to receive a certificate for a small fee. The MOOC is instructor-led, giving an opportunity to participants to learn from some of the best experts within the European supercomputing field. It can be audited free of charge and takes 5 weeks to complete, with an average of 3 hours commitment time per week. Users can also choose to receive a certificate for a small fee.

The “Element of Supercomputing” [9], which has been developed by the CSC - IT Center for Science and Kajaani University of Applied Sciences (KAMK) in Finland and has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). This free, online MOOC course is providing an introduction to supercomputing and high-performance computing. There are no prerequisites for this course, which evolves around six modules that aim to provide the fundamentals of supercomputers and HPC, and their usage via real-life examples and practical use cases. Learners can go through a short online assessment after the end of each module.

Another, free online training MOOC for High-performance computing (HPC) is also provided via Moodle platform from the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) of the University of Illinois in the

Mode of Teaching	Professional HPC Training	Professional HPC MOOC Training	Professional HPC NOOC Training
Approaches	Standalone HPC courses by design with potential for student led aggregation (Alexandrov and Sanchez, 2017) Student (home organisation) led sequence (Alexandrov and Sanchez, 2017) Diagnostic testing or attainment of practical skills based certification (Alexandrov and Sanchez, 2017)	Standalone courses by design Asynchronous, learner led Anonymous and open to all No prerequisites/entry qualifications Certification possible	Short standalone courses by design Asynchronous, learner led Anonymous and open to all No prerequisites/entry qualifications
Context	Physical	Online	Online
Entrance Requirements	Yes	No	No
Focus	Develop share knowledge and understanding	Develop share knowledge and understanding	Enhance digital competences and corporate performance
Effort/ Commitment for learner	High	High/ Medium	Low
Cost	Free- based	Free or fee- based	Free
Examples	Traditional HPC Industrial training programs	NCSA HPC MOOC Elements of Superscomputing	n/a (to our knowledge)

Table 1: Comparison of Professional HPC Training Courses

US. NCSA’s HPC-Moodle [23] focuses on HPC skills development via free self-paced courses and web-enhanced training events.

2.1.2 HPC Nano Open Online Courses (NOOCs)

Nano-MOOCs or Nano Open Online Courses (NOOCs), refer to micro courses (nano-courses), developed in a “just in time” way, indicating that “users can achieve the skills required in a short time to improve their digital competence and perform more effectively in the personal and professional spheres” [4]. NOOCs are small training doses of specific topics, maintaining the MOOC educational perspective. A key difference between the two, is the duration (estimated time) to complete the online course [4]. According to Benavidez et al., [5] the time and effort, estimated in hours and weeks, that the learner or participant requires to complete the course in a MOOC is between 32 to 72 h, whereas in a nano-MOOC is between 1 to 20 h.

A comparison of the different types of professional HPC training is provided in Table 1, taking into account the teaching mode, the context, the entrance requirements, the focus, the associated effort for the learner as well as the cost.

3 Co-creating an Open HPC Industrial Training NOOC

Aiming to adopt an open and agile approach for the co-creation of educational value [27] of this HPC industrial course, the consortium included two sub-processes: first the co-design and co-production of value emerging from this training course, and second, value beyond production in the consumption of such value, namely value-in-use [27, 21].

The idea for this course emerged from a bottom-up ideation process within the consortium partners, and in the course of the collaboration of the EuroCC project and the CASTIEL project [1], presenting initially the idea about the creation of this course, and its potential impact for industry. This initiated the creation of a small open and voluntary working group, comprised by all interested members of the consortium. Creating this way a “community of kindred spirits”, based on Pater [24] (see Figure 1), allowing anyone to join from the consortium (openness dimension) and allowing the outcomes and challenges to be owned by the initiator and the contributors (ownership dimension).

The first part of the co-creation process entailed the joint design/co-design of the course, its objectives and modules. After a number of iterations, the

Fig. 1: Types of co-creation

first part was finalised and the second part involved the co-production of the material that were utilized for the different modules and sub-modules of the course.

3.1 Course overview & Learning Outcomes

Aiming to address the needs of the industrial community, this course aims to be an online NOOC (Nano Open Online Course) course. It is modular and self-paced (form), with short presentations across different modules, targeting the needs of entrepreneurs, Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs), as well as larger organisations (target audience). It will not necessitate any prerequisites and will be made freely available to all, under a CC (creative commons) license. Its format facilitates the ongoing evolution and expansion of the initial content of the course across emerging themes and indicative success stories, etc.

The learning objectives for this course aim to: (i) provide a short, concrete overview of HPC and why it is important for business, (ii) demonstrate the potential of HPC and its industrial impact, (iii) offer an overview of the different ways that HPC can help industrial users and provide practical industrial best practices across different domains from Europe and the world, (iv) explain how an industrial user can adopt HPC and facilitate the creation of a link with the local HPC ecosystem.

The course covers three distinct modules, as seen in Figure 2, which aim to provide: (i) Module 1: “what is HPC and why it is important”, providing a short introduction to HPC for industrial users, (ii) Module 2: “HPC success stories across domains”, providing a number of success stories across domains and geographical regions in 33 distinct countries, and finally (iii)

Module 3: “Getting started with HPC” providing an overview of how an HPC-oriented approach can be adopted in the current business practices of small and medium-sized enterprises while also providing guidance and information in relation to their national HPC center(s).

The learning outcomes for each of the three modules are: (i) Module 1: increased awareness and understanding of what is high performance computing (HPC) and how advanced computing resources can be used to solve computationally intensive problems in an industrial context, as well as an understanding of the importance of HPC in today’s highly demanding business environment, and its potential impact for the European economy. (ii) Module 2: understand and recognise how HPC can be applied in different industrial domains in order to solve practical business needs (via the user-driven explorative session). (iii) Module 3: increased awareness and understanding of how a company can adopt HPC in its current practices and who are relevant stakeholders that could provide further and more specialised information.

Fig. 2: HPC learning modules – an overview

3.2 Training Modules

The training material is organized in 3 thematic areas developed as modules (see Figure 3). The modules functions in sequence and independently, enabling the user to access the information that it is seeking, rapidly and incrementally.

Fig. 3: Illustration of different modules compiled in current NOOC. The illustration is taken from the official site [12]

3.2.1 Module 1: HPC in a nutshell

In module 1, the educational goal is to provide a high-level description of the concept of HPC, the importances and the financial aspect. The material consists of videos and brief text, introducing HPC, discussing the importance of HPC from a market perspective, alongside information on the complexity of deciding what infrastructure is suited for your needs. The material comes from different online sources, such as the training hub called “Elements of Supercomputing” [9], PRACE RI [26] and DigitalEU [10].

A series of formats are utilized with the first part that presents the concept of HPC, using animation videos to explain the concept and the European HPC landscape. A very important and interesting concept for the industry is the market perspective of HPC infrastructure and use. For the latter, the material is presented in text format. The same approach is used on the third part consisting of a brief description on how to acquire an HPC infrastructure and at the same time attempts to introduce the uniqueness of HPC infrastructures as hardware (H/W) and difficulty to use it efficient. The HPC utilization is a very complex task as they have been developed with speed and efficiency in mind, and each system is tailored to specific requirements, type of algorithm and/or sector. As such, a potential user has to know the H/W is required that is dictated by the problem at hand and then allocate the most efficient infrastructure. The latter directly affect the cost of HPC use in terms of H/W and usage time.

3.2.2 Module 2: HPC Success Stories - Using HPC to solve industrial problems

This module’s goal is to advertise successful usage of HPC in industrial sectors and different fields and hint at the added value of using HPC for innovation in real world cases. As such, it serves as a database of highlights and success stories. It presents a series of diverse industrial problems that require intensive

computational resources. HPC infrastructures were utilized successfully, providing either a large number of CPUs, or GPUs, a large amount of memory, or a combination of the above. Module 2 consists of 40 success stories from 22 countries across the EU, covering 17 fields of application as it is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Fields of applications of HPC industrial success stories

Success Stories key components

The stories are diverse from different countries and from several industrial sectors. To harmonize the presentation of the information and provide a unified way to the user to access the information, a single and simple presentation format was used. The format of depicting each story is based on key elements consisting of describing the industrial problem, the need for HPC resources, the solution that HPC infrastructures provided and the benefits for the industry itself. The format is in slides presentation consisting of information about: (a) industry that HPC technology helped, (b) the problem, the solution HPC technologies provided, (c) the solution provided, (d) the benefits gained from the industry by using HPC infrastructures. The generic templates for the presentation of the different success stories, are illustrated in Figure 5.

The Greek Success Story

In the current section, a Greek success story is used as an example of the information provided by following the slide format. Figure 6 illustrates the presentation of a Greek success story of aerodynamic shape optimisation for the transport industry. The industrial partner provides a custom-made bicycle with lower drag and side forces than the baseline one. Specifically, any

is presented in Figure 7, consists of 5 research organizations with a series of service portfolios with training, HPC consultation in accessing and using HPC infrastructure, alongside consultation on funding opportunities for academia, industry and public sector.

4 Conclusion

The first public version of online NOOC is available via the main EuroCC@Greece site [12]. For the next period testing the material and asking for feedback from a small but diverse audience in order to provide a more targeted online course for HPC, is planned. The latter will be a non-stop on-going process that will help offer better quality material in every cycle of update.

Moreover, more functionalities are under consideration to be incorporated in the course that may help the user to have a more customized experience following the key concepts of the different modules. It is planned to change the presentation of the success stories by providing filtering options of field of application, country, hardware needed. As such, a potential industrial user could easily find the most relevant case to his/her sector to read and thus, understand better the added value of using an HPC infrastructure.

A lot of effort and work is planned for module 3. is envisioned to cover difficult but essential subjects for a potential industrial user of an HPC infrastructure. It aspires to provide (1) an HPC readiness framework in order to accommodate a self-assessment for estimating the level of suitability of an industrial problem to be upscaled in an HPC infrastructure, (2) a cost-benefit analysis of different options of acquiring HPC resources (in-house, cloud, national infrastructures) in terms of HPC costs associated with the infrastructure and the specialized personnel, (3) implementation guidelines and practical recommendations (i.e., CPU vs GPU, compilers, distribution of workers, etc) and (4) an overview of the skills of EU National Competence Centers (NCC) that are part of EuroCC project.

It is important to facilitate an ongoing dialogue with the industrial community regarding their HPC needs, so as to adopt accordingly the training material for the industrial courses but also for the academic courses aiming to address the shortage of qualified HPC job applicants, especially by ensuring that HPC competency is required in university scientific and engineering curricula, and that students are aware from an early age of HPC careers.

Furthermore, it is important that this NOOC remains up-to date and is enriched with emerging theme in the area of HPC (module 1), the relevant use-cases and success stories across Europe (module 2) as well as the relevant regional information across the National Competence Centers (NCCs) (module 3). In relation to module 1 for example aspects linked with the ethics of HPC will be included. These will be reflecting the ethical concerns of the HPC advances, the responsibilities with HPC applications (for example, the use of HPC to support unethical applications, etc), the role of HPC in perpetuating inequality [19] and creating an HPC digital divide [18], or the ethical issues

linked with the environmental impact of HPC [8] and the need for technological democratisation [36].

Future enhancements of the course may be linked with the creation of a broader online community of industrial HPC learners that may be linked with an online message forum, learning support from local NCCs etc. In addition, the introduction of learning credentials for this particular NOOC. In addition, short quizzes and tests may be linked with the specific course modules facilitating the acquisition of educational units that may lead to the acquisition of a certification (diploma or badge) that validates their participation in the course.

Aiming to set a basis for bridging the “HPC Digital Divide”, the current approach is an effort to co-design, co-develop and co-disseminate a complex scientific concept towards converting it into a mainstream tool, specifically for the industry so as to realise the full spectrum of HPC benefits for the economy and society at large. The proposed open, co-created industrial HPC training course aims to contribute to the democratisation of HPC training for industry and narrowing the gap between HPC adoption especially for small and medium sized enterprises, in order to reap the benefits of HPC innovations. Finally, the authors of the manuscript hope to show the value of co-creation, for addressing training asymmetries in the context of HPC, with this novel NOOC (Nano Open Online Course) course, which aims to raise industrial awareness and HPC understanding fostering this way wider adoption of advanced computing resources to solve computationally intensive problems in the business context. Leading eventually to wider access to supercomputers for scientists and engineers from the industry in addition to academia, throughout Europe and beyond. Towards this aim, it is important that EU, and national governments implement policies that foster HPC democratisation that focus not only at the infrastructural level but also at the skills development/educational level for different stakeholders.

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A Greek Success Story in 'Aerodynamic Shape Optimisation'

SUCCESS STORY IN AERODYNAMIC SHAPE OPTIMIZATION (Greece)

<p>COMPANY BACKGROUND</p> <p>Stamatis Miaz is a Greek firm focusing on building, maintaining and optimizing marine machinery.</p>	<p>THE PROBLEM</p> <p>Design a hull for a boat with a lower drag and side force than the baseline one, included in four different operating conditions.</p>	<p>SUCCESS STORY DETAILS</p> <p>100% reduction with respect to baseline flow performance, steady streamlines, low resistance in the future CFD simulations tests.</p>
<p>THE PROPOSED SOLUTION</p> <p>The CFD problem domain falls within CFD based aerodynamic optimization.</p> <p>An algorithm should be devised that automatically evaluate and optimize hulls for geometry, given the chosen operating conditions (four operating drag and side force).</p>	<p>THE SOLUTION</p> <p>An automatic shape optimization was performed using an adjoint based gradient based optimization algorithm.</p>	<p>THE RESULTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Quantitative results ■ Physical and aerodynamic analysis of the optimized hulls ■ Always converge with a finite number of iterations

Design Innovation MCC Awards

SUCCESS STORY IN AERODYNAMIC SHAPE OPTIMIZATION (Greece)

<p>THE PROBLEM</p> <p>A class of "Stamatis Miaz" boats for a cruise-line, hulls with lower drag and side force than the one in market. Specifically, the new hulls should perform better than the current one in a range of hulls and side force values. The optimization of these operating points give rise to a multi-point, multi-objective aerodynamic optimization problem.</p>	<p>THE PROPOSED SOLUTION</p> <p>Each hulls operating features to be evaluated in four different operating conditions, using a suite of the adjoint computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solver, on a mesh consisting of 10M cells and using the CPU time. The cost of each simulation is around 10h CPU time.</p> <p>Since the evaluation of the hulls' geometry have a non-negligible CPU cost, an optimization algorithm that can handle the optimal hulls' geometry within a relatively small number of optimization cycles and a robust CFD system was required.</p>
<p>THE SOLUTION</p> <p>An adjoint based, gradient based optimization algorithm was used to solve the aerodynamic problem. In specific, the adjoint computational CFD developed by the project and used to calculate the gradients through the optimization problem.</p> <p>The two objective functions from the four operating points were considered into one, using weights provided by the industry. Iterations started from a set of the upper hulls' geometry. Each optimization cycle had a pair of about 100 iterations, keeping the solution of four flow and adjoint systems until convergence was reached (100 iterations per cycle).</p>	<p>THE RESULTS</p> <p>The adoption of an adjoint based optimization algorithm led to a small number of optimization cycles and thus, a relatively short numerical optimization time (less than 10 days without an external CPU usage).</p> <p>Aerodynamic drag was reduced in all operating points (from 2% to 5.8%), depending on the quality of the hulls. The side force almost doubled. The results were automatically validated by the flow field, reference unchanged and the flow and side force zero, with an emphasis on the former attached in order to reduce the side force.</p> <p>All the cases where done without building different hulls' geometries and resulting experiments, saving optimization costs.</p>

Fig. 6: Illustration of HPC industrial success stories format. Current presentation refers to the Greek success story of aerodynamic shape optimisation

NCC Greece Overview

NCC Greece,
May 16th, 2022

contact@eurocc-greece.gr

EURO

NCC Greece

OVERVIEW

EuroCC@Greece has a 3-fold goal to advance competitiveness in research, improve effectiveness of government services and promote innovation in industry. It is run by a consortium of 5 institutions, namely

- GENET - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology
- National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos"
- Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FOERTH)
- Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICS-FORTH)
- Technical University of Crete

PRICING POLICY / BUSINESS MODEL

NCC Greece works as first contact point for (a) framing the industry case at hand, (b) assessing the HPC readiness and (c) provide the contact information for a suitable HPC expert that can help implementing, developing and utilizing HPC resources effectively.

BUSINESS SUPPORT / SERVICES

The service portfolio of EuroCC@Greece addresses the Technology Transfer needs of the Greek HPC-oriented companies:

- Consultation on access to HPC resources
- Networking (promotion of Greek technologies abroad)
- by identifying of qualified partner for technological, business and research cooperation)
- Consultation on Funding opportunities
- Intellectual Property (IP) Management (trainings on IP issues, advice on IP assessment, management, patenting, licensing, split-off creation etc.)
- Mentoring on Business Development
- Industrial Internship (train MSc level students to use HPC resources in industrial cases as part of their Master thesis)

DESCRIPTION OF INFRASTRUCTURE

ARIS supercomputer consists of 532 computational nodes. It is a PRACE Tier-2 system offering a 520 TeraFlops computing system. ARIS empowers the Scientific Community by meeting the needs in multiple scientific fields.

TRAINING ACTIVITIES

- PRACE Training Center (PTC)
- Greek academic HPC-related courses HDB
- Industry specific training events
- Mapping Greek HPC demand & supply

NCC 11, Greece
Type: HPC/ HPC/ AI
<http://eurocc-greece.gr/>
Contact: contact@eurocc-greece.gr

Fig. 7: Presentation format of National Competence Centres (NCC) of EuroCC. The current illustration refers to the NCC Greece